

6TH CONGRESS
IWA-MEXICO
YOUNG WATER
PROFESSIONALS
2022

VIRTUAL

**6TH CONFERENCE
IWA-MEXICO
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2022**

23-27 May 2022
Culiacán, Sinaloa, México

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23-27 de mayo de 2022
Culiacán de Rosales, Sinaloa

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En este documento encontrarás la recopilación de los resúmenes en extenso de los trabajos que fueron presentados en el 6th CONFERENCE IWA-YWP MEXICO 2022, el cual se llevó a cabo de manera virtual del 25 al 27 de mayo de 2022. La Universidad Tecnológica de Culiacán fue sede de este evento. Se abordaron 15 diferentes áreas temáticas relacionadas con el recurso hídrico. Los trabajos presentados en modalidad oral los podrás ver en el Capítulo 1 y, la modalidad póster en el Capítulo 2.

En este congreso se presentaron 108 trabajos en modalidad oral y 61 trabajos en modalidad póster. También se tuvieron trabajos de 25 estados de la república y 5 países extranjeros. Todos estos trabajos fueron evaluados por miembros del comité científico, los cuales son investigadores que pertenecen al Sistema Nacional de Investigadores. Cabe mencionar que el contenido de los resúmenes en extenso es responsabilidad de quienes lo presentan como autores y no refleja ninguna postura de las Instituciones convocantes.

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1.11 GESTIÓN DEL AGUA URBANA

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1.11.1 WATER EFFICIENCY HOUSEHOLDS RETROFIT THROUGH RAINWATER HARVESTING, AN ANCESTRAL AND ONGOING DRINKING-WATER SOURCE

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Keywords: circular economy, ecotechnology, rainwater harvesting system, water sensitive cities, water quality, water stress

ABSTRACT

The objectives of this research were: i) to propose a domestic water efficiency retrofit (WER) prototype implementing a rainwater harvesting system (RWHS), ii) determine the RWHS efficiency, and iii) evaluate the social perception about the WER acceptance and implementation in a single-family household (SFH). The WER prototype was developed in a SFH. The SFH is located in the basic geostatistical area (BGA) 2736 in Acapulco, Gro. Mexico. The RWHS catchment surface area was 29 m², 50% of the total roof slab area. The device comprises a first-rain separator (20 L) and a storage tank (1,200 L). The rainwater harvesting potential (RWHP) was evaluated during two consecutive rainy seasons (2020 and 2021). The harvested rainwater quality was analyzed in samples from 2021. The water analyses carried out were alkalinity, pH, electrical conductivity, total dissolved solids, chlorides, nitrates, and sulfates. Additionally, 168 surveys were applied within the BGA 2736 to the SFH owners to evaluate their perception about the acceptance and possible reconversion of the SFH. The RWHP was ca. 44 and 20.51 L/m² in 2020 and 2021, respectively. All the quality rainwater parameters evaluated met with the NOM-127-SSA1-1994. Moreover, the perception study showed that 95% of those surveyed are willing to modify their households into a WER. The observed results were encouraging. Due to the RWHP and the harvested rainwater quality, the WER of a SFH poses as a promising eco-technological solution to address the hydric stress global issue based on the circular economy concept.

INTRODUCTION

The water stress phenomenon occurs when the extraction of water from natural sources exceeds the recharge capacity of nature. This phenomenon increases with the growth of urban areas and the demand for water to satisfy consumptive uses (Deshmukh, 2021). Currently, "alternate water sources" have gained attention. One of these alternatives is rainwater due to the quality with which it can be obtained. Rainwater harvesting systems are ancient technologies capable of contributing to the satisfaction of water demand in multiple contexts. In the urban context, roofs are an important waterproofed surface, which is why they represent an excellent opportunity for rainwater harvesting under the "water-sensitive city" and "circular economy" approaches. These approaches are based on the revaluation of water and its sustainable management (Gleason-Espíndola *et al.*, 2018). Thus, the objectives of this research were: i) to propose a domestic water efficiency retrofit (WER) prototype implementing a rainwater harvesting system (RWHS), ii) to determine the RWHS efficiency, and iii) evaluate the social perception about the WER acceptance and implementation in a single-family household (SFH).

METHODOLOGY

The WER prototype was developed in a SFH. The SFH is located in the basic geostatistical area (BGA) 2736 in Acapulco, Gro. Mexico. The RWHS catchment surface area was 29 m², 50% of the total roof slab area. The device comprises a first-rain separator (20 L) and a storage tank (1,200 L). The rainwater harvesting potential (RWHP) was evaluated during two consecutive rainy seasons (2020 and 2021). The RWHP was determined by averaging each pluvial event's captured water volume per m². The harvested rainwater quality was analyzed in samples from 2021. The water analyses carried out were alkalinity, pH, electrical conductivity, total dissolved solids, chlorides, nitrates, and sulfates. Additionally, 168 surveys were applied within the BGA 2736 to the SFH owners to evaluate their perception about the acceptance and possible reconversion of the SFH.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The RWHP was ca. 44 and 20.51 L/m² in 2020 and 2021, respectively. It was possible to capture ca. 1,276 and 595 L/rain in 2020 and 2021, respectively, by the prototype surface. It is estimated that the RWHP is higher than 900 L due to rainfall by averaging both values. In 2020, the number of rain events (20) was less than the number of precipitations recorded in 2021 (58). However, the RWHP was higher in 2020 because the rainfall recorded was of greater intensity than the rainfall recorded in 2021 (Fig. 1). In other words, considering both periods, a RWHP >36,000 L per year is estimated, which translates into a total of 33 commercial collectors of 1,100 L.

Figure 1. Rainwater catchment and rainfall intensity in 2020 and 2021 within the BGA-2736.

The construction regulations for the municipality of Acapulco consider 150 L of water to satisfy the consumptive needs per person. The National Institute of Statistics and Geography (INEGI) considers that there are 3.49 inhabitants per dwelling in the study area. These data indicate that the average consumption in the BGA-2736 per household is 523.5 L/day. The RWHP obtained is sufficient to meet the needs of an average home for ca. 70 days. In addition, the results of the physicochemical analysis evaluated and contemplated within NOM-127-SSA1-1994, water for human use and consumption, indicated that the quality of rainwater complies with the parameters established by the standard, except for pH (Table 1).

Table 1. Collected rainwater physicochemical characteristics compared with the NOM-127-SSA1-1994 established parameters.

Parameter	FRS	ST	Nom
pH	6.44	6.38	6.5-8.5
EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	46.21	86.70	NR
Alk (CaCO_3 mg/L)	7.96	9.90	300
TDS	22.99	32.00	1000
Cl^- (mg/L)	9.61	7.30	250
NO_3^-	2.06	1.81	10
SO_4^{2-}	2.08	6.75	400

Alk= Alkalinity; EC= electrical conductivity; FRS= first rain separator; ST= storage tank; TDS= total dissolved solids; NR= Not reported; Nom=NOM-127-SSA1-1994

Moreover, the perception study showed that 95% of those surveyed are willing to modify their households into a WER. The observed results were encouraging. Due to the RWHP and the harvested rainwater quality, the WER of a SFH poses as a promising eco-technological solution to address the hydric stress global issue based on the circular economy concept.

CONCLUSIONS

The achieved RWHP (>900 L) demonstrated that WER implementing RWHSs is a promising technology for water supply in urban housing. In addition, the quality of the collected water complies with NOM-127-SSA1-1994 (except for pH), and the amount of water that can be collected is sufficient to meet the needs of the inhabitants of the households for more than two months. The use of rainwater in urban single-family household's results in savings in the payment of water to the municipal company. For this reason, 95% of the inhabitants of BGA-2736 are willing to implement a WER of their single-family homes.

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